

Shri Vile Parle Kelavani Mandal's
**MITHIBAI COLLEGE OF ARTS, CHAUHAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE &
AMRUTBEN JIVANLAL COLLEGE OF COMMERCE AND ECONOMICS
(AUTONOMOUS)**
Vile Parle (W) Mumbai - 400056.

**Mirror, Mirror Shattered: Breaking the Spell of Neil Gaiman's Unreliable
Narrator in "Snow, Glass, Apples"**

Submitted by

ARIANA LALJEE

BACHELOR OF ARTS

(ENGLISH)

Semester VI

Research Supervisor

Shripad Samant

Faculty, Department of Foreign Languages

Mithibai College

(Autonomous)

Certificate

This is to certify that ARIANA LALJEE of T.Y.B.A. English,

Semester VI (2023 – 2024) has successfully completed her research paper on
Mirror, Mirror Shattered: Breaking the Spell of Neil Gaiman's Unreliable

Narrator in "Snow, Glass, Apples"

under the guidance of Mr. Shripad Samant.

Professor Shripad Samant

Ariana Laljee

Shripad Samant

UAMAENG608

31st January 2024

Mirror, Mirror Shattered: Breaking the Spell of Neil Gaiman's Unreliable Narrator in
"Snow, Glass, Apples"

"Lie so convincingly you'll believe that something has vanished into thin air."¹

- Neil Gaiman

Abstract

This paper explores the intricate landscape of 20th-century British literature, resonating with the echoes of world wars, imperial decline, and cultural shifts, through the innovative lens of genre-bending author Neil Gaiman. Specifically centred on Gaiman's "Snow, Glass, Apples," the analysis delves into his post-modern deconstruction of traditional narratives and his embrace of fragmented literary forms. Gaiman's chilling reinterpretation of the Snow White fairytale serves as a focal point, with emphasis on the Queen's unreliable narration, replete with biases, justifications, and distortions. Through this exploration, Gaiman skilfully dismantles the archetypal beauty-power-morality triad, laying bare the unsettling anxieties lurking beneath the surface of the narrative.

The study draws upon Wayne C. Booth's analytical framework in "The Rhetoric of Fiction" and employs the subversive fairytale methodology to illuminate Gaiman's adept manipulation of an untrustworthy narrator. This analytical approach sheds light on how Gaiman challenges

¹ Gaiman, Neil. *Smoke and Mirrors*. Harper Collins, 2009.

readers to confront and question deeply ingrained fairy tale conventions, providing a nuanced understanding of the narrative innovations at play.

Ultimately, the argument posits that the Queen's unreliability extends beyond a mere literary device; it functions as a transformative force within the text. The Queen's skewed perspective becomes a catalyst for profound reader engagement, urging them to approach the narrative critically, dissect its unsettling undercurrents, and re-evaluate preconceived notions about fairytales and the narratives that mould them. In essence, Gaiman's narrative strategy, embodied in the Queen's unreliability, emerges as a vehicle for broader reflection and re-examination of cultural and literary constructs.

Keywords: Neil Gaiman, Wayne C. Booth, Jack Zipes, Unreliable Narrator, Postmodernism, Fragmented Narratives, Rhetoric, Subversion, Narrative analysis, Beauty, Power, Morality.

In the tumultuous landscapes of post-colonial Britain, 20th-century British literature grappled with the profound impact of two world wars, the collapse of empires, and the transformative shifts in cultural paradigms. Amidst this fertile ground, a multitude of voices emerged, challenging established narratives and embracing fragmented literary forms. Angela Carter and Jeanette Winterson, both pioneers in their own right, wove intricate narratives that engaged with the fractured realities of the era. Angela Carter, a master of subversion, skilfully crafted tapestries of myth and allegory, while Jeanette Winterson reimaged familiar fairytales with dark satire. Within this literary tapestry, Neil Gaiman emerged as a singular force, seamlessly blending horror, fantasy, and science fiction to transfigure mythologies into unsettling reflections of the modern psyche.

What distinguishes Gaiman is his remarkable ability to defy categorization, embodying the postmodern ethos of dismantling rigid boundaries. This genre-fluid approach is vividly illustrated in "Snow, Glass, Apples,"² where he takes the archetypal fairytale of Snow White and transforms it into a chilling narrative of paranoia and self-reflection. Through the poisoned lens of the Queen's perspective, Gaiman subverts the familiar, deconstructing simplistic binaries of good and evil, and revealing the murky motives that lurk beneath surface appearances. In exploring these themes, Gaiman enriches the literary landscape, contributing to the broader conversation on the complexities of human nature and societal constructs.

This paper embarks on a profound exploration of Neil Gaiman's "Snow, Glass, Apples," delving into the intricate labyrinth of the narrative and its profound engagement with the concept of the unreliable narrator, as elucidated by Wayne C. Booth in "The Rhetoric

² ---. *Snow, Glass, Apples*. Headline, 2019.

of Fiction."³ Employing Booth's theoretical framework, the study meticulously dissects the Queen's narrative, unravelling her biases, justifications, and emotional distortions. Through this analysis, the paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how the Queen's unreliability becomes a central element shaping the reader's experience, fostering suspense, uncertainty, and a critical re-evaluation of traditional fairy tale tropes.

In tandem with Booth's framework, this research paper also adopts the methodology of subversive⁴ fairytale theory to further unravel the intricate layers of the Queen's distorted perspective. By scrutinizing the Queen's narrative through the lens of subversive fairytales, the study seeks to elucidate how Gaiman effectively subverts classical fairytales through the implementation of an unreliable narrator. The focus of this examination extends to the subversion of classic fairytale archetypes and themes related to beauty, power, and morality within the narrative. The overarching motivation behind this exploration is rooted in the enigmatic nature of the Queen's manipulative discourse, sparking intellectual curiosity to decode her motives and unveil concealed truths. Through this comprehensive endeavour, the paper aims to offer readers a nuanced understanding of the story, challenging preconceived notions and providing insights into the unsettling reflections of contemporary anxieties embedded in Gaiman's narrative. At its core, the thesis of this paper contends that the unreliability of the narrator serves as a transformative force, inviting readers to confront and question established norms within the fairy tale genre.

Before delving into the critical analysis of the plot, let's commence by exploring a concise summary and background of the short story. "Snow, Glass, Apples," penned by Neil Gaiman in 1994, stands as a dark and inventive reinterpretation of the classic Snow White

³ Booth, Wayne C. *The Rhetoric of Fiction*. University of Chicago Press, 2010.

⁴ Literary critic Louis A. Montrose writes "the capacity of the dominant order to generate subversion so as to use it to its own ends".

fairy tale. Departing from tradition, Gaiman narrates the story from the perspective of the stepmother, traditionally depicted as the wicked queen, introducing a subversive twist to the narrative. In Gaiman's rendition, the queen positions herself as a victim striving to protect her kingdom from a vampiric and predatory Snow White. This narrative choice challenges established notions of good and evil, beauty, and morality, creating a haunting and unsettling tale that delves into the complexities of power, perception, and the very nature of storytelling itself.

Born on November 10, 1960, Neil Gaiman has risen as a luminary in British literature, celebrated for his multifaceted contributions spanning fantasy, horror, and graphic novels. His literary journey gained significant momentum with seminal works such as "Neverwhere"⁵ (1996) and the critically acclaimed "American Gods"⁶ (2001). Within these works, Gaiman's distinctive writing style took shape—a fusion of lyrical prose, nuanced characterizations, and a blending of folklore, mythology, and contemporary sensibilities. Influenced by childhood readings and his groundbreaking comic series, "Sandman,"⁷ Gaiman's inclination toward subverting fairy tales became a defining element of his oeuvre. This propensity for narrative subversion, characterized by the dismantling of traditional story arcs and the infusion of narratives with shades of darkness and moral ambiguity, is notably evident in "Snow, Glass, Apples."

In the context of the discourse on Neil Gaiman's works, Tara Prescott makes an analogy in "The Anxiety of Disappearance,"⁸ where she states: "In many ways, trying to cover the works of Neil Gaiman is like trying to plot out a European vacation: you could try to hit all the major tourist spots in six countries in six days, or you could carefully scrutinize the

⁵ Gaiman, Neil, and Mónica Faerna. *Neverwhere*. Roca Editorial, 2019.

⁶ Gaiman, Neil, et al. *American Gods*. Dark Horse Books, 2018.

⁷ ---. *The Sandman. Dream Country*. Dc Comics, 2018.

⁸ Key, Michael B. "The Anxiety of Disappearance."

beautiful lichen on a stone stile in Cornwall. Both are lovely and interesting, but it is nearly impossible to have both experiences on the same journey.” (2)⁹

However, the unreliable narrator¹⁰ theory emerges as a potent lens through which to interpret Gaiman's prolific literary output. The inherent unreliability of his narrators facilitates a simultaneous exploration of grand themes and subtle intricacies, resulting in a literary landscape where major plot points and nuanced details coexist in a harmonious interplay. Moreover, this intentional narrative ambiguity serves as a powerful tool for the subversion of original story elements within Gaiman's works, transforming familiar tropes into avenues for unexpected exploration. By employing unreliable narrators, Gaiman defies conventional expectations, weaving intricate narratives that challenge and deconstruct established literary norms. The unreliability of these narrators becomes a catalyst for narrative innovation, allowing Gaiman to engage with both the macroscopic and microscopic aspects of storytelling. Contrary to Prescott's analogy, the unreliable narrator theory suggests that Gaiman's narrative approach transcends a simplistic division between major and minor elements. Instead, it fosters a dynamic interplay where the grand and the subtle converge, enriching the reader's experience. This approach not only underscores the complexity of Gaiman's storytelling but also provides a strong rationale for employing Wayne C. Booth's theory to dissect and understand the intricate layers of narrative unreliability within Gaiman's works, particularly in the analysis of "Snow, Glass, Apples."

Wayne Booth's "The Rhetoric of Fiction," a seminal work in literary theory published in 1961, stands as a comprehensive framework for analysing narrative choices and their

⁹ Prescott, Tara. *Neil Gaiman in the 21st Century : Essays on the Novels, Children's Stories, Online Writings, Comics and Other Works*. Mcfarland & Company, Inc., Publishers, 2015.

¹⁰ An unreliable narrator is an untrustworthy storyteller, most often used in narratives with a first-person point of view. The unreliable narrator is either deliberately deceptive or unintentionally misguided, forcing the reader to question their credibility as a storyteller.

profound impact on reader interpretation. This influential text delves into the rhetorical aspects of fiction, emphasizing the strategies employed by authors to communicate with readers and shape their understanding of the text. When applied to Neil Gaiman's "Snow, Glass, Apples," Booth's framework proves highly relevant and beneficial for several compelling reasons. 'In this process, most critics have attempted to secure the concept of narrative unreliability, sometimes in terms of the implied author, sometimes in other ways.' (Chatman 1978; Riggan 1981; Rimmon-Kenan 1983). Booth's own contribution lies in his rigorous and nuanced definition of the unreliable narrator, equipping readers with a powerful tool for analysing the Queen's subjective perspective and uncovering the complexities of the story. For him, as he states in "The Rhetoric of Fiction", 'a reliable narrator aligns with the implied author's norms, while an unreliable narrator deviates from them.' (Booth 1961: 158-9). This binary offers a clear starting point for understanding the Queen's position in "Snow, Glass, Apples," where her motivations and biases constantly challenge the reader's trust. The story thrives on the unreliable voice of the Queen, and Booth's framework in Chapter 6¹¹ meticulously dissects narrator types and their degrees of reliability. Concepts such as first-person limited perspective, internal monologues, and selective reporting become invaluable tools for delving into the Queen's manipulative storytelling. This analytical approach allows for a nuanced understanding of her character flaws, motivations, and ultimate downfall, revealing layers of complexity that might be overlooked without Booth's insights.

Moreover, Booth's examination of the implied author and authorial voice proves crucial for unravelling the moral dimensions of "Snow, Glass, Apples." By exploring how the implied author subtly guides reader interpretation, Booth's framework creates a fascinating tension when applied to Gaiman's work. The story, through subtle details and discrepancies, hints at a

¹¹ Booth, Wayne C. *The Rhetoric of Fiction*. University of Chicago Press, 2010. (pg- 149-166)

larger truth beyond the Queen's biased version of events, inviting readers to question her reliability and engage with themes of morality, deception, and the nature of truth.

Finally, Booth's framework aids in understanding how Gaiman strategically uses familiar tropes and subverts them, creating a unique and unsettling atmosphere that fuels the story's suspense and thematic complexity. As Jack Zipes emphasizes in "Fairy Tales and the Art of Subversion," "Fairy tales...have always been a powerful discourse, capable of being used to shape or destabilize attitudes and behaviour within culture."¹² This quote underscores the transformative potential of fairy tales and aligns with Booth's approach to analysing how Gaiman leverages and disrupts these narrative conventions.

To elucidate the rationale behind the presence of an unreliable narrator in the subversion of fairytales in general, a comparison can be drawn to Angela Carter's "The Snow Child" as an intertextual reference. Booth's example of an unreliable narrator, "Whitey," in Ring Lardner's "Haircut"¹³ aligns with the complexities introduced by Carter in "The Snow Child"¹⁴. While both narrators attempt to control the narrative, their inner struggles peek through, revealing layers of complexity. Whitey's casual racism belies deeper insecurity and fear of social mobility, while the Countesses' envy of the Snow Child's beauty and the Count's infatuation underlined with sexual innuendos is intertwined with a strange fascination. These internal conflicts prevent the reader from fully understanding or sympathizing with them, keeping their characters ambiguous and intriguing. Hence, Booth's concept of the implied author as having an "intuitive apprehension of a completed artistic whole"¹⁵ can be applied to both "The Snow Child" and "Snow, Glass, Apples."

¹² Zipes, Jack. *Fairy Tales and the Art of Subversion*. Routledge, 2011.

¹³ Ring Lardner. *Haircut*. Read Books, 2012.

¹⁴ Carter, Angela. *The Bloody Chamber and Other Stories ; Wise Children ; Fireworks*. Alfred A. Knopf, 2018.

¹⁵ Booth, Wayne C. *The Rhetoric of Fiction*. University of Chicago Press, 2010. (pg- 73)

Gaiman's reflections on storytelling become pivotal here as he asserts, "What you're doing is lying, but you're using the truth in order to make your lies convincing and true. You're using them as seasoning. You're using the truth as a condiment to make an otherwise unconvincing narrative credible."¹⁶ This insight from Gaiman sheds light on the intentional manipulation of truth within the narrative. Even the opening lines of "Snow, Glass, Apples" immediately introduce an aura of uncertainty and unreliability, challenging the reader's perception. The statement, "I do not know what manner of thing she is. None of us do,"¹⁷ establishes a tone of ambiguity, signalling that the narrator, presumably the Queen, lacks a clear understanding of the subject— the Princess, her stepdaughter. This inherent uncertainty is compounded by the cryptic assertion that she killed her mother during childbirth, with a suggestion that this alone cannot fully explain her enigmatic nature, is she human or not? The reader must read on.

The Queen's account of the Prince's arrival is a notable instance of her unreliable narration. She describes the political nuances of his entourage, attempting to contextualize the encounter. However, the excessive detail in her intimate encounter with the Prince introduces a disparity between her pragmatic motives and her intense emotional involvement. This creates an unreliable narrative, raising questions about her authenticity. As she confesses, "He rode with a small retinue: large enough to defend him, small enough that another monarch — myself, for instance — would not view him as a potential threat."¹⁸

The Queen's portrayal of her stepdaughter's return in "Snow, Glass, Apples" vividly highlights her unreliable narration. Phrases such as "And she stayed cold, and the bloom of

¹⁶ Neil Gaiman: Writing Honest Fiction Lecture

¹⁷ ---. *Snow, Glass, Apples*. Headline, 2019. (Lines 1-2)

¹⁸ ---. *Snow, Glass, Apples*. Headline, 2019. (Lines 247-248)

death remained on her lips, and his lust was not diminished in any way"¹⁹ expose the Queen's profound bias and contempt toward her stepdaughter. The detailed description of the stepdaughter's reappearance raises doubts about the accuracy of the events, prompting scepticism. The Queen's emotions, particularly her hatred and disgust, taint the narrative, indicating a skewed perspective. Additionally, the Queen's impending demise in the kiln introduces poetic justice, yet her refusal to scream and fixation on the snowflake on her stepdaughter's cheek add layers of complexity. Lines like "I will not scream. I will not give them that satisfaction. They will have my body, but my soul and my story are my own, and will die with me"²⁰ underscore her determination to control the narrative even in her final moments. This reinforces the notion that her perspective, shaped by personal biases and emotions, might not be entirely trustworthy.

Riggan's assertion²¹ that an observer-narrator is incapable of penetrating directly into the psyche of the protagonist or other characters within the chronicle further aligns with the Queen's unreliability. In "Snow, Glass, Apples," the Queen's narrative lacks a direct insight into the stepdaughter's true nature, and her biased perspective prevents a clear understanding of the characters' psyches. This limitation corresponds with Riggan's idea that observer-narrators may only report overt actions and draw inferences, making them unreliable in providing an in-depth portrayal of characters' inner lives.

Furthermore, in "Narrative Fiction" (1983), Rimmon-Kenan contributes to the understanding of the critical tendency towards unreliable narrators. She defines a 'reliable narrator as one whose rendering of the story and commentary on it the reader is supposed to

¹⁹ ---. *Snow, Glass, Apples*. Headline, 2019. (Lines 309-310)

²⁰ ---. *Snow, Glass, Apples*. Headline, 2019. (Lines 328-329)

²¹ Riggan, William F. (1981). *Picaros, Madmen, Naifs, and Clowns: The Unreliable First-Person Narrator*. Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 1981. Print.

accept as an authoritative account of the fictional truth. Conversely, an unreliable narrator is one whose rendering of the story and/or commentary on it the reader has reasons to suspect.²² Rimmon-Kenan emphasizes that indications of unreliability are easier to specify, and reliability can be negatively defined by their absence.

Further on, the Queen's unreliability extends to her depiction of the forest folk and the Spring Fair. When she describes the forest dwellers, she employs dehumanizing language, referring to them as "greedy, feral, dangerous people"²³ and emphasizing their physical deformities. The use of derogatory terms like "stunted," "huge teeth," and "vacant gazes of idiots"²⁴ reveals the Queen's biased perspective, as she portrays them as subhuman, reinforcing her disdain and fear. This characterization influences the reader's perception of the forest folk, highlighting the Queen's unreliability in providing an objective account of events. Additionally, the Queen's description of the Spring Fair and her interaction with the forest folk during the fair reveals her prejudices. Lines like "they would nail their wares to the bare boards of their stalls,"²⁵ suggesting a fear of theft, and her consideration of having the forest people killed, further showcase her mistrust and contempt, creating an unreliable narrative that reflects her paranoia and prejudice.

Gaiman's inventive use of Snow White's colour palette adds another layer to the narrative. The colours red, white, and ebony, traditionally symbolizing Snow White's beauty, are redefined in Gaiman's rendition. Red symbolizes the blood on her lips after feeding, white signifies the pallor of the undead, and black may be linked to death, sexuality, or operating

²² Shlomith Rimmon-Kenan. *Narrative Fiction Contemporary Poetics*. London New York Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group, 2011.

²³ ---. *Snow, Glass, Apples*. Headline, 2019. (Lines 98)

²⁴ ---. *Snow, Glass, Apples*. Headline, 2019. (Lines 99)

²⁵ ---. *Snow, Glass, Apples*. Headline, 2019. (Lines 105-106)

under the cover of night. The perspective shift to the King also reveals traits of unreliability. The King's portrayal as a once vigorous and loving figure is contrasted with the physical and emotional decline he experiences suddenly. The Queen describes him as becoming "dizzy, listless, confused,"²⁶ and unable to engage in intimate relations. The King's physical condition is described in stark detail, with bones showing through his skin, ancient scars covering his body, and a sense of overall decay. These details might be subjective interpretations by the Queen, and the King's perspective on his health is not provided. Additionally, the King's mysterious death is presented without a clear cause, and the circumstances surrounding his demise remain ambiguous, hinting at the act of paedophilia. The lack of a definitive explanation opens the door to interpreting the King's fate through the lens of the Queen's biased perspective, rendering the readers with no other choice.

Finally, embracing the postmodern concept of transcending the multitude of meanings and delving into the diversity of truths, readers can interpret the Queen in "Snow, Glass, Apples" as an increasingly unreliable narrator, casting doubt on every narrative she presents. Her unreliability extends to the point where she might be crafting stories to position herself as a victim and thwart her stepdaughter's claim to the throne. Alternatively, the Queen's lack of reliability could stem from mental illness, giving rise to a distorted reality. While Gaiman introduces elements hinting at vampirism, incest, and necrophilia, an alternative perspective proposes that the subverted Queen's narrative is shaped by a formative experience, possibly involving sexual abuse, leading to delusions. This perspective challenges Gaiman's explicit themes, suggesting that the Princess, far from being a vampire draining life from the townspeople, might be innocent. Perhaps the huntsmen did not take her life in the forest but left her, and she had to resort to prostitution to survive in dire conditions. This alternative

²⁶ ---. *Snow, Glass, Apples*. Headline, 2019. (Lines 50-51)

viewpoint introduces complexity to the narrative, portraying the Princess as a temporary victim ensnared by the poisonous trap laid out by the Queen.

In essence, Neil Gaiman's "Snow, Glass, Apples" emerges as a captivating exploration and reinterpretation of the Snow White narrative. The deliberate use of an unreliable narrator, embodied by the Queen, becomes a masterstroke in challenging established fairy tale norms. Gaiman's storytelling artistry intricately weaves a narrative tapestry that blurs the lines between reality and fantasy, urging readers to scrutinize the subjective nature of truth. Through shifts in perspective and symbolism, the story becomes a profound exploration of power dynamics and identity. As we navigate this multidimensional landscape, Gaiman invites us to question traditional constructs, fostering a nuanced appreciation for the complexities within character relationships.

However, the "masterstroke" of using an unreliable narrator isn't without its challenges. As literary theorist Seymour Chatman suggests, unreliable narration can create a certain dissonance between the narrator's account and the reader's expectations. This "ironic form," as Chatman calls it, forces us to "read out" between the lines and question the narrator's credibility. In "Snow, Glass, Apples," the Queen's biased perspective and manipulative language become our clues to discern the "real" story behind her fairytale facade.²⁷

Ultimately, Gaiman's masterful use of the unreliable narrator invites us to engage in a deeper level of literary analysis, encouraging us to critically examine the construction of truth and challenge our preconceived notions about familiar narratives. This is where the true magic of "Snow, Glass, Apples" lies: not just in a retelling, but in a deconstruction and reconstruction

²⁷ Chatman, Seymour (1990). *Coming to Terms: The Rhetoric of Narrative in Fiction and Film*. Ithaca and London: Cornell University Press.

that demands thoughtful reinterpretation and fosters a more nuanced understanding of timeless tales.

Works Cited

- Kemp, Peter. "English Literature - the Modernist Revolution." *Encyclopedia Britannica*, www.britannica.com/art/English-literature/The-Modernist-revolution.
- Ray, Michael. "Neil Gaiman". *Encyclopedia Britannica*, 15 Dec. 2023, <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Neil-Gaiman>. Accessed 31 January 2024.
- . *Snow, Glass, Apples*. Headline, 2019.
- Snow, Glass, Apples – Original Text | Shortsonline*. 9 May 2019, xpressenglish.com/our-stories/snow-glass-apples/. Accessed 31 Jan. 2024.
- Apple of My Eye: Gaiman's "Snow, Glass, Apples" – the Channel*. mcgillchannelundergraduaterewiew.com/2018/04/apple-of-my-eye-gaimans-snow-glass-apples/. Accessed 31 Jan. 2024.
- BabyWrites. "Neil Gaiman's 'Snow, Glass, Apples': Here's My Hot Take... It's Really about Rape (Not Vampires)." *Medium*, 6 June 2022, babywrites.medium.com/neil-gaimans-snow-glass-apples-here-s-my-hot-take-it-s-really-about-rape-not-vampires-3dc5b51a54fa. Accessed 31 Jan. 2024.
- Booth, Wayne C. *The Rhetoric of Fiction*. University of Chicago Press, 2010.
- Booth, Wayne C. "The Rhetoric of Fiction." *Google Books*, University of Chicago Press, 1983, books.google.co.in/books/about/The_Rhetoric_of_Fiction.html?id=VfUgMbRYSW4C&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false. Accessed 31 Jan. 2024.
- Carter, Angela. *The Bloody Chamber and Other Stories ; Wise Children ; Fireworks*. Alfred A. Knopf, 2018.
- Gaiman, Neil, et al. *American Gods*. Dark Horse Books, 2018.

“Neil Gaiman: Writing Honest Fiction.” *Www.linkedin.com*, www.linkedin.com/pulse/neil-gaiman-writing-honest-fiction-shelby-fielding/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_android&utm_campaign=share_via. Accessed 31 Jan. 2024.

Prescott, Tara. *Neil Gaiman in the 21st Century : Essays on the Novels, Children’s Stories, Online Writings, Comics and Other Works*. Mcfarland & Company, Inc., Publishers, 2015.

Shlomith Rimmon-Kenan. *Narrative Fiction Contemporary Poetics*. London New York Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group, 2011.

“The Narrator in Wayne C. Booth’s the Rhetoric of Fiction | Bartleby.” *Www.bartleby.com*, www.bartleby.com/essay/The-Narrator-In-Wayne-C-Booths-The-11C8800ADC72C215. Accessed 31 Jan. 2024.

Zipes, Jack. *Fairy Tales and the Art of Subversion*. Routledge, 2011.

Álvarez-Amorós, José. (2021). Revisiting ‘Third-Person’ Narrative Unreliability: Wayne C. Booth and the Bases for an Inclusive Approach to Unreliable Narration. *Poetica*. 52. 361-386. 10.30965/25890530-05201015.

Murphy,, Terence Patrick. "Defining the reliable narrator: The marked status of first-person fiction" *Journal of Literary Semantics*, vol. 41, no. 1, 2012, pp. 67-87. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jls-2012-0004>

Šurkalović, Josipa. *Neil Gaiman’s Subversive Fairy Tale Revisions-“Snow, Glass, Apples” and “The Sleeper and The Spindle”*. Diss. University of Zagreb. Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences. Department of English language and literature, 2022.

Schnitzler, Laura-Marie. “Fantasy’s Traumatic Take on the Bildungsroman:Reading Neil Gaiman.” (2020).

Adams, Faith, "Neil Gaiman's Elevated Fairy Tale: Childhood Trauma Through the Lens of Postmodernism" (2023). Student Works. 1.

https://digitalcollections.lipscomb.edu/eml_student/1

Ferry, James, "The Unreliable Narrator: Simplifying the Device and Exploring its Role in Autobiography" (2017). Masters Theses. 463. <https://doi.org/10.7275/9500156>
https://scholarworks.umass.edu/masters_theses_2/463

"A Bibliography of Publications by Jack Zipes on Fairy Tales, Fantasy, and Children's Literature."

Marvels & Tales, vol. 16, no. 2, 2002, pp. 132–39. *JSTOR*,

<http://www.jstor.org/stable/41388623>. Accessed 31 Jan. 2024.

Klapcsik, Sándor. "Neil Gaiman's Irony, Liminal Fantasies, and Fairy Tale Adaptations." *Hungarian*

Journal of English and American Studies (HJEAS), vol. 14, no. 2, 2008, pp. 317–34. *JSTOR*,

<http://www.jstor.org/stable/41274433>. Accessed 31 Jan. 2024.